

Progress Report and Research Report

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1 Progress

arXiv:1807.11234: This paper is on a deep atrous convolutional encoder-decoder we developed for transmission electron micrograph (TEM) denoising. In the paper, the network is shown to considerably outperform lay implementations of traditional denoising methods. Nevertheless, there are small systematic errors due to the time-variance of interpolation during training. These are very small, making them difficult to see on an absolute scale, so we emphasize them using contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization. Several example applications to TEM images are presented. We also provide several examples of scanning transmission electron micrograph (STEM) denoising to demonstrate the ability of our network to generalize to domains it has not been trained for.

To make the network easy to train from scratch or fine tune, we designed it to be trained end-to-end; rather than in parts. This is challenging as the network is very deep, consisting of an Xception backbone, atrous spatial pyramid pooling module and multi-stage decoder. To surpass our benchmarks, we therefore tried many training hyperparameters, learning protocol and architecture variations. Learning curves for several of these are presented in the paper. The network has a high capacity and was L2 regularized during training, making it suitable for continued training. Pre-trained models for low- and high-dose electron micrographs are available via the network's GitHub repository: <https://github.com/Jeffrey-Ede/Electron-Micrograph-Denoiser>.

arXiv:1808.09916: This paper is on 40+ autoencoders, kernels and multilayer perceptrons we trained for electron micrograph data compression and denoising. Perhaps surprisingly, no prior work seems to have been done on dedicated autoencoders, kernels and multilayer perceptrons for electron microscopy. Consequently, this paper focuses on the effects of basic architectural variations on performance. These studies were carried out for TEM and STEM separately for completeness. Our code and pre-trained models are available via <https://github.com/Jeffrey-Ede/Denoising-Kernels-MLPs-Autoencoders>.

Realistic super-compression: We have invented a new process that uses neural networks to super-compress images. We have developed it for TEM and STEM images and can compress them by more than an order of magnitude without significant information loss. Importantly, the restored images are realistic with correct noise characteristics and textural detail. We believe the process has applications in all areas of image super-compression; not just electron microscopy.

Warwick Ventures has approved the pursuit of a patent so we are reluctant to provide too many details. However, we will say that realistic decompressions are achieved using a generative adversarial network with multiple discriminators. We have trained 10+ variations for TEM and STEM compression ratios between 10 and 100. Each network now only takes a couple of days to train as a result of advances we have made in training hyperparameters, learning protocols and architecture. Mode collapse is now a non-issue. The paper has been drafted (20+ pages), along with an ancillary paper (35+ pages; needs some work). However, we are not publishing until we have talked to a patent agent about our process when he visits in a few weeks.

First 6 months: Work done in the first 6 months of my PhD is detailed in my 6 month progress report. That is available at <https://v1.overleaf.com/read/dbnxmpmwjtyt>. The largest project involved automating/accelerating the reconstruction of large angle convergent beam electron diffraction patterns and has its own GitHub repository: <https://github.com/Jeffrey-Ede/Beanland-Atlas>.

2 Research Plan

Research projects we are working on at the moment include

VAE-GAN: We are developing a variational autoencoder-generative adversarial network (VAE-GAN) for high-level semantic manipulation of electron micrographs. It will have ancillary uses as a search engine, for data compression and as a feature extractor. Unlike other VAE-GANs that typically encode small (e.g. 32×32) images, we have developed a generative adversarial network with multiple Wasserstein discriminators and novel loss functions to encode 256×256 or larger images.

Part of our approach is to use an atrous spatial pyramid pooling module at output stride 16 to distill the semantic information used for encoding; rather than the output stride 32 vectors typically used for image classification. The spatial dimensions in our encoding remove the need to unnaturally encode spatial information in a vector, making learning easier. Nevertheless, we are experimenting with a VAE-GAN inside the VAE-GAN that will develop a vector suitable for non-spatial high-level semantic manipulation from the spatial semantics of the outer VAE-GAN.

A history of discrimination: We saved 5.4 GB of discriminators' imagination when training one of our super-compression networks. No detailed studies have yet been carried out on the imagination of GAN discriminators, in spite of increasing interest within the machine learning community. Among other reasons, this is because discriminators are typically shallow networks: their imagination looks nothing like the deep dreams of classification networks that have been studied so far. Importantly, this study is about more than imagination: it will give new insights into electron micrograph Hamiltonians.

Accelerated CBED simulation: Convergent beam electron diffraction (CBED) patterns currently take tens to hundreds of seconds to simulate. We are therefore developing a deep neural network to accelerate their calculation. This project is especially fun as features come in different forms, making the feature engineering challenge significant. For example, thickness and energy are scalars whereas crystal potentials are images. We are confident that we can train a neural network to calculate CBED images one-at-a-time. If we assume a terrible inference time of 100 ms, this would accelerate the calculation by at least an order of magnitude. We are hoping to develop a neural network to calculate all the output images simultaneously, accelerating the calculation by multiple orders of magnitude; however, it is not yet clear if our hardware can support the number of neurons needed to stabilize the calculation.

3 Other

I have completed the following MPAGS modules:

- PX904: Properties and Characterisation of Materials (2 credits)
- PX905: Defects and Dopants (2 credits)
- CH978: Surfaces, Interfaces and Coatings (2 credits)

I have completed all the year 1 doctoral skills tasks.